

Efficacy of Early Use of CPAP and Prophylactic Surfactant in Preterm Having Respiratory Distress Syndrome

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: The most common cause of respiratory distress in newborn is respiratory distress syndrome and respiratory distress syndrome is common cause of morbidity and mortality in preterm neonates. The current study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of locally developed BUBBLE CPAP as a non-invasive strategy for managing respiratory distress in newborns within resource-limited settings.

Material and Methods: Present Prospective interventional study conducted on Preterm babies' birth with respiratory distress syndrome at A tertiary care hospital and medical college, Bhuj, Gujarat, India. A total 96 eligible babies were included in this study. Need for intubation, need for surfactant therapy, Hospital stay and Mortality. Immediate complication like Pneumothorax and Pulmonary hemorrhage were recorded.

Results: The study involved 96 preterm newborns, with 43.8% between 34-36 weeks gestational age, 35.4% weighing between 1-1.5 kg, 52.1% females, and 47.9% males. Of these, 67.7% were inborn and 32.3% were outborn, with 30.2% having a hospital stay between 6-10 days. Regarding CPAP administration, 69.7% received early CPAP, while 30.3% received delayed CPAP. Antenatal steroid coverage varied, with 5.2% having full coverage, 29.9% partial, and 65.6% no coverage. Surfactant administration was as follows: 9.4% received prophylactic, 8.3% late rescue, 16.7% early rescue, and 66.6% no surfactant. Intubation was required for 39.5% of the newborns, while 60.5% were not intubated.

Conclusion: The findings highlight variations in outcomes based on the timing and type of surfactant administration, emphasizing the risks associated with intubation and the potential benefits of early CPAP in reducing need of surfactant, mortality, intubation, hospital stay, complications.

Keywords: Continuous Positive Airway Pressure, Intubation, Preterm, Respiratory Distress Syndrome.

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Introduction

Neonatal period is defined as up to first 28 days of life and further divided into very early (birth to <24 h), early (birth to <7 days), and late neonatal period (7 days to <28 days). [1] Neonatal period is the most vulnerable period of human life as it accounts for very high morbidities and mortalities and most of these are preventable. India accounts for approximately 20% of worldwide live births but experiences over 25% of neonatal mortality cases. [2] In developing nations, there exists a dearth of research on the etiology of respiratory distress in neonates, often leading to the initial management of all neonatal respiratory distress cases as pneumonia at the primary care facility. [3] The neonatal mortality rate (NMR) in India is 26 per 1000 live births. [4] Respiratory distress emerges as a prevalent disorder encountered during the neonatal period, typically within the first 48-72 hours of life. Its incidence approximates 7% (with a range of 5-

10%) among infants. [5] Respiratory pathology stands as the most frequent (32-54%) postmortem discovery among early neonatal fatalities. [6] The spectrum of neonatal respiratory distress encompasses pneumonia, transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTNB), respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), and meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS). Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), formerly known as hyaline membrane disease (HMD), describes a disease typical of preterm infants that is caused by generalized atelectasis of alveoli due to insufficient pulmonary surfactant. The most common cause of respiratory distress in newborn is respiratory distress syndrome (hyaline membrane disease) and respiratory distress syndrome is common cause of morbidity and mortality in preterm neonates. Deficiency of pulmonary surfactant is one of the most important factors contributing to the development of RDS. In

premature lungs, the increased surface tension due to a deficit in surfactant culminates in alveolar collapse upon exhalation, atelectasis, uneven lung inflation, and localized alveolar overexpansion. Left untreated, this sequence leads to epithelial damage and pulmonary edema, exacerbating the impairment of surfactant function and manifesting the characteristic clinical presentation of RDS. [7] Continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) is a type of positive airway pressure that is used to deliver a set pressure to the airways that is maintained throughout the respiratory cycle, during both inspiration and expiration. The application of CPAP maintains PEEP, can decrease atelectasis, increases the surface area of the alveolus, improves V/Q matching, and hence, improves oxygenation. [8]

CPAP started within the delivery room and OT immediately after preterm baby born with respiratory distress syndrome. Surfactant replacement therapy (SRT) plays a pivotal role in the management of neonates with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) because it improves survival and reduces respiratory morbidities. Prophylactic surfactant therapy given within 30 min of delivery of neonates with respiratory distress syndrome.

Insufficient awareness and suboptimal implementation of antenatal steroids contribute to the frequent occurrence of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) in premature infants. Early use of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) represents a cost-effective, straightforward, and non-invasive solution, particularly in countries like India where invasive ventilation may not be readily available in many locations.

With the anticipated decrease in the cost of surfactant, combining early CPAP with surfactant therapy, when necessary, could emerge as a significant advancement for preterm care in India. The current study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of locally developed BUBBLE CPAP as a non-invasive strategy for managing respiratory distress in newborns within resource-limited settings.

Material and Methods

Present Prospective interventional study conducted on Preterm babies' birth with respiratory distress syndrome at A tertiary care hospital and medical college, Bhuj, Gujarat, India. The data collected over period of 1 year from April 2023 to April 2024. All the preterm neonates admit in GKGH hospital having respiratory distress syndrome were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Not willing parents
2. Neonates having another congenital anomaly
3. preterm neonates who are intubated at the time of birth

Approval was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) in order to perform the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all parents included in the study. Sample size was estimated by using $Z^2 \cdot pq/n^2$. A total 96 eligible babies were included in this study.

Study Procedure

Early CPAP given to the inborn babies and outborn babies are in to category of late CPAP because of outborn referred from primary or secondary healthcare center or private gynec hospital. Prophylactic surfactant is administered to extremely preterm and very preterm neonates diagnosed with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) who exhibit FiO_2 requirements exceeding 30% and a Silverman anderson score (SAS) is 6 or greater than 6, in conjunction with a positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) of 6. Early rescue surfactant is administered within 2 hours of life to both inborn and outborn babies exhibiting FiO_2 requirements greater than 30% and a Silverman anderson Score (SAS) exceeding 6, alongside radiographic evidence indicating a change consistent with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) on chest X-ray. Primary outcomes measures were: Need for intubation, Need for surfactant therapy, Hospital stay and Mortality. Immediate complication like Pneumothorax and Pulmonary hemorrhage were recorded.

Failure of NCPAP is indicated by one or more of the following:

1. A sustained requirement for a $FiO_2 > 0.40$ on CPAP of 7 cm H₂O
2. Absolute rise in FiO_2 of 0.10 or greater over a timeframe not exceeding two hours
3. Respiratory acidosis pH < 7.25 with a rising PaCO₂ > 60 mmHg on an arterial or capillary sample
4. Development of recurrent apnoea requiring stimulation
5. Development of spontaneous episodes of significant desaturation (<91 per cent for > 20 seconds)
6. Increased recession and tachypnea
7. Agitation not relieved by simple measures (comforting, repositioning)

Statistical analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were described as means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range based on their distribution. Qualitative variables were presented as count and percentages. For all tests, confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of Gestational age

Gestational age	Frequency	Percentage
28 - 30	19	19.8%
31 - 33	35	36.6%
34 - 36	42	43.8%
Total	96	100%

Out of total 96 participants in our study, 43.8% were of 34-36 weeks of gestational age, 36.6% belonged to the 31-33 weeks gestational age group, and 19.8% belonged to 28-30 weeks gestational age.

In our study, out of total 96 Newborns, 35.4% had Birth weight between 1-1.5 kg, 32.3% had between 2.1 – 2.5 kg, 29.2% had between 1.6-2 kg, and 3.1% had BW between 2.6 – 3 kg. Out of total 96 participants, 52.1% were females and 47.9% were males. Out of total 96 newborns, 5.2 % had full ANC

steroid coverage, 29.9% had partial coverage, and 65.6% had no Ante-natal steroid coverage.

Out of total 96 participants, early CPAP was administered to 69.7% of Newborns, and Delayed CPAP was administered to 30.3% newborns. In our study, only 9.4% had prophylactic surfactant administration, 8.3% had late rescue, 16.7% had early rescue and rest 66.6% did not receive any surfactant.

Table 2: Surfactant Administered vs Birth Weight

Surfactant Administered	Birth Weight			
	1 – 1.5 kg	1.6 – 2 kg	2.1 – 2.5 kg	2.6 – 3 kg
Not Administered	8	22	31	3
Early Rescue	11	4	0	0
Late Rescue	5	2	0	0
prophylactic	9	0	0	0
Total	34	28	31	3

Out of total 64 newborns, who had no surfactant administration, maximum number, 31 of them belonged to 2.1-2.5kg birthweight group, In 15 newborns with early rescue, maximum number 11, of them belonged to 1-1.5kg birthweight group, In 8 newborns with late rescue, maximum number 5 of them belonged to 1-1.5 kg birthweight group, and in 9 newborns with prophylactic surfactant administration all of them were in 1 – 1.5 kg birthweight group. Out of total 96 newborns, 39.5% were intubated and 60.5% were not intubated. Out of total newborns in our study, 81.3% had no complications, 6.3% had IVH, 5.2% had

pneumothorax, 4.2% had BPD, and 3.1% had pulmonary hemorrhage. In our study, 30.2 % of participants had duration of hospital stay between 6 – 10 days, 28.1% between 1-5 days, 19.8% had between 11-15 days, 14.6% had > 20 days and lastly 7.3% had hospital stay between 16 – 20 days. Out of total 96 newborns taken in our study, 72.9% were discharged, while 27.1% expired. Out of total 19 newborns belonging to 28 – 30 weeks GA group, 8 were discharged and 11 expired, 35 belonged to 31-33 weeks GA, amongst them 24 were discharged and 11 expired, and 42 belonged to 34-36 weeks GA , amongst them 38 were discharged and 4 expired.

Table 3: CPAP vs Duration of hospital stay

Hospital Stay	CPAP	
	Early	Delayed
1 – 5	29.85%	24.13%
6 – 10	32.83%	24.13%
11 – 15	19.40%	20.68%
16 – 20	7.46%	6.89%
>20	10.44%	24.13%
P value	0.001	

Amongst Newborns having 1-5 days hospital stay, 29.85% had early CPAP administered and 24.13% had delayed, in 6-10 days group, 32.83% had Early CPAP and 24.13% had delayed, in 11-15 days group, 19.40% had early CPAP , 20.68% had delayed, in 16-20 days group, 7.46% had early CPAP and 6.89% had delayed CPAP, and in

Newborns having more than 20 days hospital stay , 10.44% had early CPAP administration and 24.13% had Delayed CPAP administration. Out of total 64 newborns, who had no surfactant administration, 10 were intubated, In 15 newborns with early rescue, 5 were intubated, In 6 newborns with late rescue, all of them were intubated, and in 4 neonates with

prophylactic surfactant administration all of them were intubated.

Table 4: Complication vs Surfactant administration

Complications	Surfactant administration			
	Prophylactic	Early rescue	Late Rescue	No
None	2	10	4	62
BPD	1	2	0	1
IVH	2	1	3	0
Pneumothorax	3	1	0	1
Pulmonary Haemorrhage	1	1	1	0
P value	<0.001			

In newborns having BPD, 2 had early rescue, none had late rescue 1 had prophylactic and 1 had no surfactant administered. In Newborns having IVH, 1 had early rescue, 3 had late rescue, 2 had prophylactic surfactant administration. In Newborns with pneumothorax, 1 had early rescue, none had late rescue, 3 had prophylactic and 1 had no surfactant administration. In Newborns having Pulmonary hemorrhage, 1 had early rescue, 1 had late rescue, and 1 had prophylactic surfactant administration.

Discussion

Endotracheal intubation can occasionally result in respiratory tract damage, bradycardia, or hypoxia. In addition to causing lung injury, mechanical ventilation (MV) has the potential to exacerbate or develop bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD). The INSURE technique (Intubation Surfactant administration Extubation) is now widely promoted, with current trends choosing to avoid intubation. Previously, the "traditional" method of surfactant administration through the endotracheal tube by intubation followed by MV was used exclusively.

The aim of our study was to study clinical outcome of preterm neonates having respiratory distress syndrome with use of early CPAP and prophylactic surfactant. We had total 96 Newborns in our study, out of them 43.8% were between 34-36 weeks of gestational age, 35.4% had Birth weight between 1-1.5 kg, 52.1% were females and 47.9% were males, 67.7% were inborn and 32.3% were outborn, 30.2% of participants had duration of hospital stay between 6 – 10 days, early CPAP was administered to 69.7% of Newborns, and Delayed CPAP was administered to 30.3% newborns, 5.2% had full ANC steroid coverage, 29.9% had partial coverage, and 65.6% had no Ante- natal steroid coverage, only 9.4% had prophylactic surfactant administration, 8.3% had late rescue, 16.7% had early rescue and rest 66.6% did not receive any surfactant, 39.5% were intubated and 60.5% were not intubated, 81.3% had no complications, 6.3% had IVH, 5.2% had pneumothorax, 4.2% had BPD, and 3.1% had pulmonary hemorrhage, 72.9% were discharged, while 27.1% expired. In our study, out of total 96 Newborns, 81.3% had no complications, 6.3% had

IVH, 5.2% had pneumothorax, 4.2% had BPD, and 3.1% had pulmonary haemorrhage. In a study done by Jaya Balaji et al Nasal Trauma, Hypotension, Intra Ventricular Hemorrhage and CPAP belly were the most common complications, occurring in 80% (70.6% to 89.4%), 11.4% (4% to 18.9%) and 10% (3% to 17%) of neonates each respectively. The other complications observed were CPAP belly, oliguria, septal injury, metabolic acidosis etc. No case of pulmonary hemorrhage was reported in the study. [9] Out of total 19 newborns belonging to 28 – 30 weeks GA group, 8 were discharged and 11 expired, 35 belonged to 31-33 weeks GA, amongst them 24 were discharged and 11 expired, and 42 belonged to 34-36 weeks GA, amongst them 38 were discharged and 4 expired, there was significant correlation between gestational age and outcome ($p < 0.001$), this findings are similar to another study done by Sneha Reddy et al where they found out In babies who were between 28-30 weeks < there is 41.67% success and 58.30% failure rate. There is statistically significant difference between success and failure groups with respect to gestational age ($p < 0.001$).

In our study, out of total 96 Newborns, Early CPAP was administered to 67 Newborns, out of them 19 were intubated and Delayed CPAP was administered to 29 Newborns, out of them also 19 were intubated, Amongst Newborns having 1-5 days hospital stay, 20 had early CPAP administered and 7 had delayed, in 6-10 days group, 22 had Early CPAP and 7 had delayed, in 11-15 days group, 13 had early CPAP, 6 had delayed, in 16-20 days group, 5 had early CPAP and 2 had delayed CPAP, and in Newborns having more than 20 days hospital stay, 7 had early CPAP administration and 7 had Delayed CPAP administration, Out of total 67 Newborns with Early CPAP, 52 were discharged and 15 had expired, and out of 29 Newborns with Delayed CPAP, 18 were discharged and 11 had expired. In a study done by Jaya Balaji et al [9] The incidence of CPAP failure was 30% (95% CI 19.3% to 40.7%) in study population, The proportion of neonates who required surfactant was 18.6% (9.5% to 27.7%), Who developed ROP was 37.1% (25.8% to 48.5%) and the proportion of children, who met with mortality was 7.1% (1.1% to 13.2%). Gittlemen

et al [10] in his study, found out that the frequency of endotracheal intubation was lower, Multiple logistic regression showed that the lower frequency of intubation was not only associated with high GA ($P=0.0003$) and a high 5minApgar score ($P=0.0008$) but also with use of early CPAP ($P=0.0064$). In our study, out of 96 Newborns, in 64 had no surfactant administration, 5 were intubated, in 15 newborns with early rescue, 6 were intubated, in 8 newborns with late rescue, in 5 neonates intubated, in 9 newborns with prophylactic surfactant administration ($p<0.001$), while in a study done by Amari et al no infant who succeeded on CPAP in the study received replacement surfactant. The proportion of infants who received surfactant in the ventilator-started group was equal to that in the CPAP failure group (53%vs51%, $OR=1.1$, 95%CI 0.5, 2.6). In our study, out of 96 Newborns, 64 newborns, who had no surfactant administration, 60 were discharged and 4 of them expired, In 15 newborns with early rescue, 7 were discharged and 8 of them expired, In 8 newborns with late rescue, 2 were discharged and 6 of them expired, and in 9 newborns with prophylactic surfactant administration, 1 was discharged and 8 had expired. ($p<0.001$). Charles A Friedman et al [11] in his study Bubble Nasal CPAP, Early Surfactant Treatment, and Rapid Extubation Are Associated with Decreased Incidence of Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia in Very-Low-Birth-Weight Newborns: Efficacy and Safety Considerations, showed that CPAP with with early surfactant treatment reduced the need for mechanical ventilation and decreased BPD.

Conclusion

Prophylactic surfactant administration decreases the rate of intubation, hospital duration, mortality, and immediate complications such as pneumothorax and pulmonary hemorrhage compared to late rescue surfactant therapy. However, there is no significant difference in the development of chronic complications like BPD between these approaches. Prophylactic surfactant is not significantly superior to early rescue surfactant therapy. Overall, early use of CPAP combined with early rescue surfactant therapy results in better outcomes and is more cost-effective for preterm neonates with RDS.

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